

Distributed Ledger Technologies for Food Sustainability indexing

Georgios Gkogkos^a, Patrícia Lourenço^{b,c}, Eleftheria Maria Pechlivani^{a,*}, Luís Encarnação^b, Konstantinos Votis^a, Nikolaos Giakoumoglou^a, José Marques da Silva^{b,c}, Dimitrios Tzovaras^a

^a Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, Information Technologies Institute, 6th km Harilaou-Thermi, Thessaloniki, 57001, Greece

^b AgroInsider Lda., R. Circular Norte, Edif. NERE, Sala 113, 7005-841, Évora, Portugal

^c MED - Mediterranean Institute for Agriculture, Environment and Development & Departamento de Engenharia Rural, Escola Ciências e Tecnologia, Universidade de Évora, Pólo da Mitra, Ap. 94, 7006-554, Évora, Portugal

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ABSTRACT

The agro-food industry currently faces increasing environmental, social, and economic challenges, emphasizing the need for an effective assessment of food sustainability. While existing certification schemes serve to evaluate food production systems' sustainability, they are often complex, laborious, and prone to errors and result in a transparency deficit and a lack of trust in the process. This paper introduces a novel solution using Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) to facilitate certificate generation and verification, with the goal of contributing to the attainment of the European Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Leveraging Blockchain technology, the solution creates an unalterable record of food sustainability certificates that can be verified with ease, enhancing efficiency, transparency, and trustworthiness in the certification process. The feasibility of the proposed DLT approach is demonstrated through a proof-of-concept implementation, which shows that the proposed solution can significantly improve the certificate generation and verification process. The resultant framework presents a secure and reliable solution for food sustainability certification, which can benefit various stakeholders in the food industry, such as producers, retailers, and consumers. The proposed DLT solution promises a significant transformation in generating and verifying food sustainability certificates, fostering more sustainable food production systems.

1. Introduction

Considering the growing environmental, health, and socioeconomic concerns over the misuse of dangerous pesticides and fertilizer, as well as the loss of nutrients, the current food and agricultural systems demand a fundamental transformation. Industrial agriculture is mostly accountable for the depletion of natural resources resulting from an increase in population and demand for food production [1]. Agri-food companies are developing carbon-neutral approaches to establish future objectives to reduce carbon emissions according to the European Green Deal towards no net emissions of greenhouse gasses (GHG) for a more sustainable food policy [2]. As agriculture is strictly dependent on the natural environment and changes in rainfall and increasing temperature extremes, implementing a carbon strategy will protect stakeholders from the adverse consequences of climate change on agriculture, thereby protecting the supply chain. The strategy may focus on decarbonization options, such as, better land use management, nitrogen

efficiency, precision agriculture, decentralized food chains and distributed food manufacturing [3]. Thus, food sustainability is essential to ensuring food security for the growing global population while also reducing the impact of food production on the environment and promoting sustainable development [4].

In this sense, it is crucial to evaluate food production systems, whether they are more intensive or less intensive, to understand their absolute and relative environmental footprints. This assessment serves as a means to continuously enhance their performance, benefiting both the companies involved in food production and the scarce resources that require constant protection [5]. For instance, a food production company may not be climate-neutral as a whole, but it can still be considered climate-compliant in terms of its product (CO₂eq/ton of tomato produced) because it is below the average for its region, when compared to its peers that produce the same type of food. The search for greater efficiencies in the use of resources per ton of food produced is a challenge that must be registered and encouraged, thus improving the footprints

* Corresponding author

E-mail addresses: ggogos@iti.gr (G. Gkogkos), patricia@agroinsider.com (P. Lourenço), riapechl@iti.gr (E.M. Pechlivani), luis.encarnacao@agroinsider.com (L. Encarnação), kvotis@iti.gr (K. Votis), ngiakoumoglou@iti.gr (N. Giakoumoglou), rafael@agroinsider.com (J.M. da Silva), dimitrios.tzovaras@iti.gr (D. Tzovaras).

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(e.g., CO₂, water, diffuse pollution, biodiversity, landscape) associated with each food produced.

In addition to the less positive aspects associated with food production, agriculture also has positive externalities in its activity, which should also be mentioned. Through agricultural activities: CO₂ can be immobilized in the soil or in the forest; reducing the risk of fires by controlling weeds and/or other types of fuel in the forest; the creation of water mirrors in the landscape for purposes associated with irrigation, they also become sources of water and food for native or migratory species; the inefficiency of food harvesting machines often leaves tons of food per hectare on the ground or in the trees which in turn serve as food for many species that benefit from it.

In recent years, the agricultural sector has witnessed a revolutionary penetration of digital technologies that have dramatically transformed farming operations and processes [6,7]. Among these, the agriculture and organic food sustainability sector has progressively embraced Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) in an effort to create a more transparent, efficient, and sustainable supply chain [8]. DLT ensures secure and accurate records through cryptography and consensus among computers, reducing the need for a central authority [9]. Moreover, DLT utilizes the technology of smart contracts. Smart contracts are automated agreements that trigger actions on DLT platforms based on pre-defined rules. These contracts are executed automatically by the DLT network when certain pre-defined conditions are met. They enhance the use of DLT in organic food certification by automating and streamlining the certification process.

By providing a secure and transparent record of transactions and data, DLT can enable greater traceability and accountability in the food supply chain, thereby reducing food waste, improving food safety and increasing the efficiency of food production and distribution. DLT can also facilitate the tracking of environmental and social impact indicators, such as greenhouse gas emissions, water use, and fair labor practices, allowing for better decision-making and monitoring of progress towards sustainability goals [10]. In addition, DLT controls food quality, thereby lowering the danger of food-borne illnesses and ensuring consumers have access to high-quality food products. By utilizing DLT to generate a tamper-proof record of each step of the supply chain, businesses and consumers can assure that the items they purchase have been cultivated and harvested in an environmentally benign and sustainable manner [11]. This information can subsequently be made available to consumers, enabling them to purchase food goods with knowledge [12]. With DLT, the certification procedure can be shortened and made more cost-effective, facilitating the market entry of small and medium-sized organic food producers [13]. This can encourage the expansion of the organic food business and boost customer confidence in organic products [14].

On the other hand, many barriers have contributed to the mistrust of organic food consumers and limited its expansion. This can be particularly damaging for small-scale farmers who rely on crop income for their livelihood [15]. Moreover, there is a risk of counterfeit organic crops. Counterfeit organic crops can weaken consumer faith in the veracity of organic claims and lower demand for legitimate organic crops, negatively affecting the profitability of farmers that cultivate these products [16].

In this context, a solution for food traceability has been developed, which calculates the CO₂ emissions and footprints of crops and generates a comprehensive index known as the Food Sustainability Index (FSi). FSi represents the overall environmental impact of the crops and is utilized by farmers to assess the carbon product footprint of their products. FSi enables farmers to compare crop production footprint with their peers who produce the same type of crop to know if they are below or above the average for their region. In this way, farmers will be encouraged to improve the footprints (CO₂, water, diffuse pollution, biodiversity, landscape) associated with each crop produced and achieve the European Farm to Fork and Green Deal objectives. FSi is based on emissions equations created by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

(IPCC), which has produced assessment reports, methodology guidelines for national GHG inventories, special reports, and technical papers. From 1991 until 1999, the IPCC Task Force on National Greenhouse Gas Inventories (TFI) based in Japan administered the IPCC National GHG Inventories Programme in close coordination with the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the International Energy Agency (IEA). The primary purpose of the IPCC was to evaluate scientific, technical, and socioeconomic data pertinent to the understanding of human-induced climate change, its possible implications, and mitigation and adaptation strategies.

This study presents a DLT-based solution for the supply chain of organic crops that promotes transparency, traceability, and accountability. The suggested approach generates a digital signature for the parameters of organic crops, which provides a secure and transparent method for farmers to validate the legitimacy of organic claims. This paper's contribution is twofold. First, it presents a DLT-based solution for the supply chain of organic crops that promotes transparency, traceability, and accountability, hence boosting customer confidence in the veracity of organic claims. Second, the study presents an Agro-food system for generating certificates that sign organic crops, based on the FSi. The proposed DLT solution for the organic crop supply chain enhances transparency, reduces fraud, and builds customer trust. It encourages sustainable practices, automates verification, and improves quality control. This transformative solution increases accountability and expands the organic crop market.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of the existing work in the field of DLT and smart contracts in Agriculture. Section 3 discusses the pertinent background information relevant to the study. Section 4 outlines the process of generating food sustainability parameters, specifically focusing on CO₂ emissions and presents the proposed solution's DLT architecture. Section 5 exhibits the results obtained from the study. Finally, Section 6 presents the conclusions drawn from the research.

2. Related Work

In recent years, there has been significant attention given to the application of DLT and smart contracts in the agricultural sector, with the aim of enhancing transparency, efficiency, and sustainability. In addition, a large body of work connected to the FSi has been reviewed in order to provide a full overview of the present research in these domains and to clarify how the first two technologies can be integrated into the organic food indexing.

Food Sustainability indexing is an emerging research field that focuses on developing metrics and indices for evaluating the sustainability of food systems. It aims to provide a holistic view of the sustainability of food production and consumption, including economic, social, and environmental dimensions. The Sustainable Food Systems Index (SFSI) combines indicators related to nutrition, environment, society, economy, and food loss and waste to provide an overall measure of the sustainability of national food systems [17]. Similarly, the Food Sustainability Index (FSI) combines indicators related to food waste, sustainable agriculture, and nutritional challenges to rank countries according to the sustainability of their food systems [18]. These composite indices provide a comprehensive view of food sustainability, which can be used to guide policy development and decision-making.

Research in the field of food sustainability indexing also encompasses the development of indicators and metrics to monitor progress and identify areas for improvement in specific aspects of food sustainability that focus on specific aspects of sustainability. Food indicators have been developed to measure the sustainability of food supply chains [19], the environmental impact of food production [20], and the social impact of food systems [21]. Belini et al. [22] used machine learning techniques to analyze data on households' food waste and identified key factors contributing to food waste, which can be used to develop targeted interventions to reduce waste.

In addition, regarding DLT, this technology has established its presence in the agricultural sector with a wide range of applications. The majority of research on DLT technology has been on technological acceptability, often neglecting the impact of DLT on supply chain sustainability. Kalamaris et al. [23] investigate the impact of DLT technology on the agriculture and food supply chain, show active projects and initiatives, and discuss the implications, challenges, and promise of the technology as a whole. Moreover, DLT approaches on supply chain provide real-time food tracking and security assurance for business resource utilization [24–26]. In addition, Casado-Vara et al. [27] proposed a solution to enhance the relationships between the members of the supply chain and provide information to consumers about the origin of the products, thus enabling the concept of circular economy. In India, Yadav et al. [28] reveal the barriers of DLT adoption in agriculture supply chain and provide suitable measures to overcome these obstacles.

Other approaches leverage the immutability of DLT to evaluate its feasibility and performance in supply chain [29,30]. Mavilia et al. [31] examine the use case of South Africa and indicate that DLT, in the e-agricultural context, has the potential for reshaping the entire sector, contributing also to the resolution of the food crisis. Additionally, many solutions try to address the issues of trust, scalability, traceability and share amount assignment in agricultural supply chain systems and develop a consortium establishment via DLT technology [32–34].

Extending the functionality of DLT, the use of smart contracts automates the verification process and reduces the time and effort required for farmers to demonstrate the organic origin of their crops. Through supply chain transparency and accountability, smart contracts enable farmers to demonstrate the value of their products, ensuring fair compensation for their crops, proving the veracity of organic claims, and distinguishing organic products from conventional crops, thus providing producers with a market advantage.

Smart contract technology is being used in certificate management systems across various domains. Zhang et al. [35] provide an overview of blockchain technology and analyze the potential challenges in implementing a blockchain-based renewable energy certificates transaction process. Furthermore, many solutions propose Blockchain-based schemes, focusing on certificate revocation management and status verification [36–38]. Other implementations present Blockchain-based systems for certificate digitalization, authenticity verification, credibility enhancement and sharing [39–42].

3. Background

The conventional process for organic food certification can be tedious and pose challenges. However, the emergence of DLT has the potential to enhance this process by improving traceability. When combined with the integration of Earth Observation (EO) systems, it becomes possible to gather crucial data on crop productivity across a variety of scales, providing further assistance in the organic certification process.

3.1. Organic Food Certificate Generation

Obtaining organic certification for farm products is a rigorous and time-consuming process that requires adherence to strict organic standards. The certification process typically involves a third-party certification agency that evaluates the farm or production facility, its practices, and its products against established organic standards. The certification process for organic food involves several steps [43,44]:

- **Pre-application:** Farmers who want to obtain organic certification for their products must first verify that their operation is eligible for certification. They need to submit an application to the certification agency and provide detailed information about their farm or production facility, including the size of the operation, the crops grown

or animals raised, and the methods used for pest control, fertilization, and weed management.

- **On-site inspection:** Once the certification agency receives the application, they will conduct an on-site inspection of the farm or production facility. The inspection is carried out by a trained inspector who will verify that the farm or facility is complying with organic standards. The inspector will check the fields, crops, soil, and water sources, and also review the farm's record-keeping practices.
- **Certification decision:** After the on-site inspection, the certification agency will make a decision about whether to grant certification. The decision will be based on the findings of the inspection, as well as the farmer's application and record-keeping practices. If the certification agency determines that the farm or facility is in compliance with organic standards, the farmer will be granted organic certification.
- **Annual inspection and certification renewal:** Organic certification is not a one-time process. Farmers must undergo an annual inspection to maintain their certification. The certification agency will conduct an annual inspection to verify that the farm or production facility is still in compliance with organic standards. The farmer will need to renew their certification annually by submitting an application and paying a renewal fee.

The goal of organic certification is to ensure that the products meet specific organic standards and are free of harmful chemicals and additives.

3.2. DLT-signed Organic Parameters

DLT has recently emerged as a powerful tool for enabling traceability in various sectors, including organic food systems [45]. By leveraging DLT, various aspects of organic food production and supply chains can be recorded and validated and transparency, traceability, and trust in the organic food ecosystem can be enhanced, as presented in Fig. 1. These parameters include organic certification, farming practices, supply chain traceability, IoT information, and lab test results. These parameters are signed and stored on a DLT Network, providing participants with increased confidence in the authenticity and quality of organic products. This technique contributes to promoting sustainable practices and fostering trust in the organic food industry.

DLT technology brings an enhanced level of transparency to the organic food industry by simplifying the documentation and validation of organic data. It empowers farmers to credibly demonstrate their crops' organic nature and value, thereby promoting supply chain accountability and ensuring fair remuneration. The use of DLT-based smart contracts streamlines the verification process, reducing the time and effort farmers spend on establishing their crops' organic status and facilitating their participation in the organic market. Moreover, the introduction of a digital signature system underpinned by DLT bolsters consumer trust in organic claims, potentially boosting demand for organic crops and increasing profitability for the farmers who grow them.

While there have been promising results, there is considerable scope for further research to enhance its application and efficiency.

3.3. Earth Observation Systems

DLT technology has found significant application in advancing Earth Observation (EO)-based systems, which offer critical data that assists the organic certification process. EO-based systems are used to access information on crop productivity, such as optical (passive) and radar (active) sensors data, at different spatial, spectral, and temporal scales resolution, from local to global scale, with or without costs [46]. Spectral imaging has demonstrated significant effectiveness when it comes to crop monitoring [47]. One crucial EO data source is the Copernicus program, a European Space Agency (ESA) initiative that provides insights on vegetation structure, crop productivity, and plant water

Fig. 1. Comparing the innovation of DLT with existing recording methods.

content. One such tool is the AgroRadar^{*}, which is based on ESA program and is a sophisticated software infrastructure visualized through the SmartAG[†] application that capitalizes on this data [47]. By leveraging artificial intelligence algorithms, AgroRadar automatically downloads and processes Copernicus satellite data, including Sentinel-1 (Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data) and Sentinel-2 (optical data), offering big data and deep learning capabilities for crop information [48]. Operating on a weekly basis, AgroRadar scrutinizes parcels across any geographic region to detect crop anomalies in space and time.

4. Materials and Methods

In order to comprehensively evaluate the EO-based systems, a 26,509m² parcel in Murcia Spain from Centro de Demostracion y Transferencia Agraria el Mirador S.COOP (CDTA) was used as a pilot demo site. From April to July of 2022, AgroRadar acquired satellite imagery, enabling the calculation of crucial vegetation indices. These indices contributed towards calculating a FSi, which was subsequently incorporated into a DLT.

4.1. Data Gathering

Multi-source EO data from the Copernicus program data/services from ESA were used, such as the SAR (active) sensor, the Sentinel-1 and the optical (passive) sensor, the Sentinel-2 to improve crop monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV). For the analysis, AgroRadar was used, which was visualized via the SmartAG application. The spatial resolution was 10m pixels and temporal resolution was ± 5 days for both sensors. From Sentinel-1, the cross-polarization (VH) [49] was used. From Sentinel-2, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) were calculated. NDVI is the fraction of the difference and the sum of the NIR and red bands where chlorophyll absorbs red whereas the mesophyll leaf structure scatters NIR [50]. It varies between 1 and -1, where 1 corresponds to high photosynthetic activity and -1 to the absence of vegetation. NDWI is related to NIR and short-wave infrared (SWIR) bands and quantifies the crop moisture content through vegetation water indices [51]. It varies between 1 and -1, with 1 corresponding to a high amount of water in the leaves (no water stress) and -1 no water in the leaves (high water stress).

During the crop campaign from April to July of 2022, a total of 49 satellite images were used to calculate vegetation structure (VH; 27 images of Sentinel-1), NDVI and NDWI (22 images from Sentinel-2 and) in the pilot's experimental open field plots.

4.2. FSi Calculation

FSi is an advanced tool developed to compute the CO₂, NPK, and water footprints of crops, thereby enhancing food traceability. Its computation methodology draws upon the emissions equations delineated by the IPCC, which feature in their assessment reports, methodology guidelines for GHG inventories, special reports, and technical papers. To calculate the FSi, farmers provided essential data such as crop area and productivity, irrigation water usage, fuel quantity, fertilizers, crop residues (accounting for direct emissions), and volatilized and leached Nitrogen (accounting for indirect emissions) [48]. These parameters facilitate the calculation of the CO₂, water, and nutrient (NPK) footprints associated with each crop.

Farmers utilize FSi as a performance indicator to gauge the efficiency of their products in terms of CO₂, water, and NPK footprints. For instance, it enables farmers producing identical crops to compare their footprint metrics against regional averages, promoting competitiveness and sustainable practices. The use of FSi encourages farmers to optimize the footprints (CO₂, Water, and Non-point source pollution) associated with their food production, aligning with the objectives of the European Farm to Fork and Green Deal initiatives.

In order to analyze the footprint of the produced crops in open fields, data provided by the pilot were used, related with the emissions in the production of pepper and tomato, such as the quantity of fuel combustion, urea application, fertilizer and crop residue. Based on these data, the FSi was calculated, i.e., the CO₂ and N footprints of the latter crop production.

4.3. DLT Implementation

The proposed approach highlights how a DLT can be used to tackle the present problem of validating digital assets. Hyperledger Sawtooth [52] was implemented. Hyperledger Sawtooth is a scalable and secure platform for the development of complicated DLT applications [53]. It employs a unique consensus technique known as "Proof of Elapsed Time (PoET)" that enables secure and efficient consensus among network nodes. Also, its modular design makes it easy to meet specific needs for a given use case and to upgrade or maintain the network as necessary.

In this case, Sawtooth was preferred over other Hyperledger frameworks due to its modularity for evolving needs, customizable consensus mechanisms, and smart contract flexibility in JavaScript language and domain-specific logic, making it suitable for agriculture. It offers scalability through parallel processing and seamless upgrades, all while maintaining enterprise-grade features. The Sawtooth network consisted of three nodes each one running one validator, which processes the transactions and holds the ledger, a REST API, a consensus engine, a set of transaction processors, which refer to the business logic of the application, and all were connected in a common MySQL database. All these components were deployed as a set of Docker containers. Sawtooth offers a REST API that enables clients to interact with validators using normal HTTP/JSON protocols. This pragmatic RESTful API provides a

* <https://business.esa.int/projects/agroradar-1>

† <https://smartag.agroinsider.com/>

language-independent interface for submitting transactions and reading blocks. The Sawtooth REST API is meant solely as a minimal client interface. It merely forwards each request to the validator for authorization with signature verification as described by the transaction processor.

The architecture of Hyperledger Sawtooth consisted of several components, as shown in Fig. 2, including:

- **Transactions:** Transactions are the basic building blocks of the DLT network. They represent changes to the state of the network and are processed and validated by nodes in the network.
- **Transactions Processor:** The Transactions Processor is responsible for processing transactions and updating the state of the network. It implements the SLP, which provides a simplified interface for writing and deploying smart contracts.
- **State Database:** The State Database is a key-value store that keeps track of the current state of the network. It is updated by the Transactions Processor whenever a transaction is processed.
- **Consensus:** Consensus is the process by which nodes in the network agree on the state of the network. Hyperledger Sawtooth uses the PoET consensus algorithm, which allows for secure and efficient consensus among nodes in the network.
- **Validators:** Validators are nodes in the network that are responsible for processing transactions and maintaining the state of the network. They run the Transactions Processor and participate in the consensus process.
- **Clients:** Clients are nodes in the network that initiate transactions and interact with the network. They send transactions to the network, which are then processed and validated by the Validators.

- **Ledger:** It is the decentralized ledger that records all transactions and state updates in the network. It is maintained by the Validators and can be accessed by Clients for reading and querying purposes.

The framework deployed four transaction processors. The two of them are build-in to the system and they were responsible to apply changes to on-chain settings (“settings-tp”) and configure consensus handling the network with its nodes (“poet-tp”). The two custom transaction processors were deployed for creating user wallets (wallet-tp), and for storing and validating (logging-tp) the FSI and the evidences combined for its generation. To create user wallets, first, the API implementing the logic for handling transactions for creating client wallets and storing personal information for the user and their agricultural infrastructure, is invoked. The API was responsible for handling the creation of the client wallet, extracting the client’s information from the transaction, validating it, and storing it in the wallet. The wallet-tp also calculates the address of the client’s wallet and stores the client’s information in the wallet. Afterwards, for a specific user’s wallet, the API of logging-tp is invoked to store the evidences for food sustainability along with the FSI calculated based on these evidences and, also, to generate the final certificate verifying all the provided data.

4.4. Data Verification

This section demonstrates the implementation of the two custom Hyperledger Sawtooth transaction processors and presents the procedure, from the registration of a user in the DLT, to the generation of the final food sustainability certificate. The two custom transaction processors take advantage of the flexibility and performance of Sawtooth to create a certificate generation process that is tailored to this specific use case, including custom validation checks, data structures, and

Fig. 2. Proposed DLT architecture with custom transaction processors.

integration with external systems and services. This innovation can result in significant improvements in efficiency, accuracy, and security of the certificate generation process, as well as greater interoperability and integration with other systems and services. There are three main stages in this process. At the first stage, the evidences and the FSI are stored in the ledger to ensure immutability. Afterwards, this, DLT verified, data is requested from the ledger to create the final certificate, and finally the certificate is produced implementing data visualization methods.

Starting from the identity management, presented in Fig. 3, a client has to register into the DLT Network to be able to interact with it. By invoking the wallet-tp to create their wallet, the client provides their credentials and some metadata related to its agriculture infrastructure. With this process, the client registers in the DLT Network and becomes a Sawtooth “Transaction Signer”, meaning they are able to submit transactions to the Ledger. Additionally, a response is sent to the client, from the DLT, including the status of the registration and their wallet ID. The wallet ID is unique for every client registered into the DLT Network. For the last step, the client makes a request to the wallet-tp, using their wallet ID, to retrieve a JSON Web Token (JWT) to use it as authorization parameter in the second stage, when invoking the logging-tp to store their data.

In the next phase, illustrated in Fig. 4, the client makes a request to the logging-tp to store the data into the Ledger, using their JWT for authorization. The data includes the sustainability evidences for the field, the agriculture procedures followed to extract these evidences, the generated FSI and information regarding the parcel. As an internal process of the logging-tp, the provided data is encrypted and stored in the Ledger. After the submission of this transaction, a response is returned to the client including the encrypted data. Finally, a request from the client is sent to the logging-tp to decrypt the encrypted message and use the data to create the FSI certificate.

All the above, summarize the data integrity verification functionality of the transaction processors ensuring the immutability of the information stored into the Ledger. By storing the sensitive data into the DLT and, as a next step, retrieving it to generate the FSI certificate, it is harder for a malicious entity to tamper with it.

Once the evidences verification is complete, the FSI certificate can be generated that confirms the crops and the field meet the proposed standards. This certificate is created using web design technologies, which link the data to the certificate. The certificate includes information about the field, the production process, details about the evidences and, of course, the final FSI. The certificate also includes a unique

fingerprint, generated from the DLT, to make it easy to track and verify.

To ensure the authenticity of the certificate, it is verified using blockchain technology. The certificate is added to a blockchain network, which provides a tamper-proof and transparent record of the certificate’s creation and verification. The network verifies each transaction on the blockchain. This ensures that the certificate remains valid and trustworthy, and that farmers can be confident in the authenticity of the organic claims they produce. The certificate is then made available, through a Decision Support System (DSS) or an application, to the farmer. The farmer can then access the certificate and give it to a certifying agency to validate that it meets organic standards.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1. FSI Evidences

From the analysis of vegetation indices (VH, NDVI and NDWI) in space and time, i.e., at the beginning and end of the campaign, there were differences in plant development within small plots (Fig. 5). In the beginning of the campaign, the vegetation indices were lower (NDVI between 0.06 and 0.09; NDWI between 0.04 and 0.07; VH between -21,22 and -16,71) compared to the end of the campaign (NDVI between 0.22 and 0.46; NDWI between 0.08 and 0.16; VH between -15,38 and -14,83). From the analysis of the plots, differences are observed in the growth patterns between pepper and tomato individually, as well as between the two crops, with tomatoes exhibiting higher values compared to peppers. The vegetation indices allowed the detection of crop anomalies, such as water stress, nutrient deficiency, and pest, which can negatively impact crop yield and quality.

In order to analyse the emissions and footprint of the open fields produced crop, data related with the emissions in the production of pepper and tomato in Murcia region of Spain were used, both conventional and organic. The FSI was calculated, based on the quantity of fuel combustion, urea application, fertilizer, and crop residue direct and indirect emissions. The results are presented in Table 1 and correspond to the total emissions and the CO₂ footprint of the pilot’s crop production in 2022.

The CO₂ footprint of conventional pepper and tomato was higher (0.17 tonCO_{2eq} and 0.12 tonCO_{2eq} respectively) than the organic pepper and tomato (0.06 tonCO_{2eq}; Table 1). The N footprint for conventional pepper and tomato was 0.1 tonCO_{2eq} and for organic pepper and tomato was 0.01 tonCO_{2eq} (Table 1). The pepper (conventional and organic) footprint was higher (0.07 tonCO_{2eq}/ton crop) than the tomato footprint

Fig. 3. Wallet creation for Client (wallet-tp).

Fig. 4. Data storage into Ledger (logging-tp).

Fig. 5. Daily evolution in space and time of the productivity (NDVI), water in plant (NDWI), and vegetation structure (VH) in the beginning (10-04-2022) and in the end (14-07-2022) of pepper (P) and tomato (T) campaign in the pilot’s experimental open field plots.

Table 1

Emissions and footprint CO₂ data of conventional and organic pepper and tomato production in Murcia (Spain) to calculate the Food Sustainability index (FSi) for food traceability.

CROP	Area ha	Productivity ton/ha	Fuel		Direct Emissions from Land Use			Indirect Emissions from Land Use		Emissions tonCO _{2eq}	Footprint		
			Quantity l	Emissions tonCO _{2eq}	Fertilizers		Harvest waste ton CO _{2eq}	N volatilized tonCO _{2eq}	N leached ton CO _{2eq}		Total tonCO _{2eq}	Area ton CO _{2eq} /ha	Crop ton CO _{2eq} /ton crop
					tonN	ton CO _{2eq}							
Conv. Pepper	0.035	72.9	6.77	0.02	0.0062	0.05	0.0004	0.0020	0.1022	0.1722	4.9188	0.0675	
Organic Pepper	0.035	24	7.93	0.02	0.0026	0.01	0.0001	0.0003	0.0345	0.0630	1.7985	0.0749	
Conv. Tomato	0.06	89.4	10.65	0.03	0.0115	0.09	0.00	0.0034	0.005	0.1229	2.0473	0.0229	
Organic Tomato	0.06	72.5	16.07	0.04	0.0047	0.01	0.00	0.0005	0.0027	0.0584	0.9732	0.0134	

which varies between 0.02 (tonCO_{2eq}/ton crop) (conventional) and 0.01 (tonCO_{2eq}/ton crop) (organic), presented in Table 1. These FSi results show differences between crops and within crops. This is a very important result because consumers can decide which product to buy based on information accumulated in the FSi, i.e., the footprint and sustainability of the food in the farm, covering different sustainability production parameters (CO₂, Water, nutrients).

The fluctuations in vegetation indices (VH, NDVI, and NDWI) between the campaign's start and end result from a blend of factors influencing plant growth, including changing growth stages, environmental conditions, water availability, nutrient uptake, pest and disease effects, management practices, and plant phenology. These combined elements lead to variations in the indices, reflecting the dynamic development of the crops over time.

From the analysis of Table 1 and Figure 5, it is observed that the productivity was higher in conventional pepper and tomato, with a great productivity difference between the conventional and the organic pepper. The conventional pepper presented lower crop footprint (0.0675 tonCO_{2eq}/ton crop) than the organic pepper (0.0749 tonCO_{2eq}/ton crop), while organic tomato showed lower crop footprint (0.0134 tonCO_{2eq}/ton crop) than the conventional tomato (0.0229 tonCO_{2eq}/ton crop). In sum, pepper production was more efficient in terms of footprint per crop (ton CO_{2eq}/ton crop) than tomato production. Analyzing the emission factors, those that polluted the most and adopted improvement actions can be identified to reduce the crop production CO₂ footprint, as is the case of N leached in pepper production.

5.2. Certificate Generation

Once the evidences are created, are sent to the Ledger, through the Blockchain's API. After the transaction is validated and committed to the ledger, the parameters are stored in a secure and immutable format. Afterwards, to retrieve these parameters, a request to the Ledger is

committed. The data then are retrieved and generate an FSi certificate ensuring that the data presented in the certificate is valid. A summary of the farmer and his infrastructure is provided on the certificate, along with the CO₂ evidences and the final FSi, clarifying the presented results. The document certificate is generated using visualization techniques, such as HTML, CSS3 and Python, in a format that is easily shareable, such as a PDF or HTML file, and it is used to provide insights into the farming operations.

The FSi food certificate is used to ensure that the products met specific food sustainable production standards namely in CO₂, water, and NPK footprints. The FSi certificate uses smart contract technology and certificates management systems across various domains. This process involves 4 steps: 1) Pre-application; 2) On-site inspection; 3) Certification decision; 4) Annual inspection and certification renewal [54,55]. In this way, the data is structured and organized so that a certifier can quickly certify the veracity of crops production, providing producers with a market advantage. The transparency of the food supply chain inside a farm is promoted through the recording of the evolution of crops campaign registered in time and space using Earth Observation data and local georeferenced evidences of the crops. These data support FSi that is calculated based on agricultural production factors emission data and which is protected through DLT, creating a smart certificate. In this way, transparency and trust throughout the farm food chain is ensured.

Georeferenced evidences (images) from the pepper and tomato production were taken by the farmers during the crop campaign period using the SmartAG mobile app. Records of georeferenced evidence strengthen the crop traceability of food production systems inside of a farm towards a clearer crop traceability process and more transparent to a consumer trust, as shown in Fig. 6. (a). The data collected through EO, georeferenced evidences, FSi and protected with smart certificates is well structured, relevant and reliable for a certifier to use and issue a certificate with social value.

As depicted in Fig. 6 (b), the certificate was generated utilizing

Fig. 6. (a) Transparency process of the supply chain from product in the farm to the final consumer. (b) Example visualization of FSi certificate in pilot's field.

JavaScript that provides farmers with critical data into crop production, thus empowering them to make informed decisions about their practices and augmenting the sustainability of their operations. The FSI, calculated according to the methodologies outlined in Section 4, extends over a scale of [-1, 1]. Values closer to "-1" are indicative of more sustainable crops, whereas those nearing "1" signify unsustainable crop practices. For instance, as per the certificate for the demo pilot site (Fig. 6 (b)), a FSI of 0.0675 suggests that the crop is sustainable. This allows them farmers to increase efficiency, decrease waste, and improve their operations' sustainability when comparing with the benchmarks of their peers.

6. Conclusions

DLT technology has the potential to revolutionize the agriculture industry by offering a safe and transparent solution for tracking and managing the production and distribution of crops. This technology can assist in addressing some of the industry's difficulties, such as inefficient supply chain management, lack of data and information integration, and restricted access. Particularly, the application of DLT technology in the issuance of certifications and the signature of organic claims can give farmers and other supply chain stakeholders with various benefits. The DLT-based certificate can boost consumer confidence in organic products by offering a secure and transparent approach for tracking the organic status of crops, while guaranteeing that farmers are rewarded appropriately for their work.

In addition, the DLT-based certificate can give farmers with useful data and insights into the production of organic products, allowing them to make more informed decisions and improve the sustainability of their operations. Not only may this assist the farmers, but it can also contribute to the general sustainability of organic agriculture, a fundamental objective for many in the business. In view of these advantages, the use of DLT technology in agriculture, namely in the issuance of certificates and signature of organic claims, represents a promising possibility for the industry to increase the production and distribution of organic commodities.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Georgios Gkogkos: Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Patrícia Lourenço:** Data curation, Resources, Formal analysis, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Eleftheria Maria Pechlivani:** Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Luís Encarnação:** Investigation, Software. **Konstantinos Votis:** Software. **Nikolaos Giakoumoglou:** Writing – review & editing. **José Marques da Silva:** Methodology. **Dimitrios Tzovaras:** Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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